

Effect of intercropping and spacing of linseed with mustard and tomato on the incidence of insect pests*

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ABSTRACT

Intercrops of linseed & mustard and linseed & tomato were infested with different species of insect pests of which the mustard aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kalt.), linseed gall midge, *Dasyncura lini* Barnes, black aphid, *Aphis craccivora* Koch, and tomato fruit borer, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner), showed significant differences in infestation levels in various intercrop situations. However, there was a general downward trend in infestation level of different pests in intercrop combinations compared to their numbers in sole crops of preferred host. The intercrops were thus, found to be more suitable for natural suppression of pest populations.

The introduction of high yielding varieties, more use of fertilizers, monocropping and indiscriminate use of pesticides have given a new dimension to pest problems. The traditional cultural practices, like intercropping, crop density manipulation, mixed cropping, crop rotation, etc. are known to take care of insect-pest species in many crop situations. Intercropping is considered as a tool of pest management as it is known to cause reduction in pest populations without polluting the associated environment (Theuniss *et al.* 1992, Lal 1991). However, very little information is available on the effect of inter-cropping of different field crops on pest populations in these crops. The present investigation was carried out to generate information on the effect of intercropping of linseed with mustard and tomato on the major pest species of these crops.

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